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D1 Collaborative Governance Framework

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This document is the POTENT-X D1 deliverable. The deliverable constitutes a unified framework that integrates stakeholder value creation, resource optimization, and communication strategies, designed to foster efficient governance and collaborative partnerships within Living Lab networks for the clean energy transition in ports.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable (D1) presents the Collaborative Governance Framework developed within the POTENT-X project to guide and support the clean energy transition in European ports. As vital nodes in global trade and economic activity, ports are also major energy consumers and carbon emitters. The transition to cleaner, smarter, and more sustainable port operations is not only essential for meeting climate goals but also for enhancing competitiveness, resilience, and community well-being.

The deliverable addresses the objectives of Task 1.3 (Stakeholder Engagement and Governance Models) and Task 1.4 (Policy and Regulation Alignment). These tasks aim to:

- Identify existing governance challenges and gaps in the current port transition landscape.
- Promote the adoption of more participatory and collaborative approaches.
- Ensure consistency between port-level actions and broader EU policy frameworks.

The framework emphasizes a multi-stakeholder approach involving public and private sector actors, academia, and civil society to co-create, implement, and refine innovative solutions. Key pillars include Stakeholder Engagement C Value Creation, Resource Optimization C Technology Integration, Communication C Knowledge Transfer, Governance C Policy Alignment, and Innovation through Living Labs. Each section outlines specific actions, strategies, and enabling mechanisms, from digital twin models and regulatory sandboxes to clean energy financing and workforce upskilling. This initiative aims to align with the European Green Deal, Fit for 55, FuelEU maritime, and the IMO's decarbonization targets, leveraging funding instruments such as Horizon Europe and CEF Transport, using two port study cases: Port of Aalborg and Port of Trelleborg.

The report functions as a strategic and operational guide for stakeholders, showing how to co-create governance models, coordinate technology deployment, and manage social and regulatory challenges in real-world port environments.

1 Introduction

The transition to clean energy in European ports is a critical enabler of the European Union's broader climate neutrality objectives, as outlined in the European Green Deal, the Fit for 55 Package, and the REPowerEU plan. As pivotal nodes in Europe's maritime and trade infrastructure, ports handle over 70% of the EU's external trade and approximately 35% of internal market trade by volume (European Commission, 2020). These facilities, however, are also major consumers of energy and contributors to local air pollution and carbon emissions. Decarbonizing port operations is therefore an urgent priority—not only to meet EU climate targets but also to enhance energy security, improve air quality, and strengthen the global competitiveness of European maritime industries.

The purpose of this report is to present a Collaborative Governance Framework designed to facilitate the clean energy transition in European ports. Ports are critical to Europe's trade and economy but are also significant sources of carbon emissions. The POTENT X project aims to address this by:

- Promoting inclusive, multi-stakeholder governance (Quadruple Helix model: public, private, academia, civil society),
- Supporting the implementation of Living Labs in pilot ports (Aalborg and Trelleborg),
- Integrating digital tools, smart energy solutions, and circular economy practices,
- Aligning port governance with EU and international climate policies (e.g., European Green Deal, Fit for 55, IMO targets),
- Serving as a scalable model for other European ports navigating similar transitions.

The report functions as a strategic and operational guide for stakeholders, showing how to co-create governance models, coordinate technology deployment, and manage social and regulatory challenges in real-world port environments.

European ports face a uniquely complex landscape: they must simultaneously modernize aging infrastructure, integrate fluctuating renewable energy sources, and comply with an evolving regulatory environment that includes the EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) extension to the maritime sector (effective from 2024), the FuelEU Maritime Regulation, and the Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation (AFIR). These requirements necessitate coordinated, multi-actor responses that extend beyond conventional governance models. Traditional hierarchical or siloed decision-making approaches are increasingly inadequate in addressing the multi-dimensional challenges of the clean energy transition. The clean energy transition in ports is a complex challenge that requires coordinated action among diverse

actors. Traditional governance models often fall short in addressing this complexity, particularly in the face of rapidly evolving technologies and policies.

In this context, collaborative governance emerges as a robust alternative. Collaborative governance offers an alternative by integrating the knowledge, resources, and priorities of multiple stakeholders through shared decision-making processes. This model facilitates the co-creation of policies, solutions, and investments by integrating the resources, expertise, and priorities of diverse stakeholders—port authorities, shipping lines, energy companies, technology providers, researchers, municipal governments, and civil society actors. Collaborative governance emphasizes inclusiveness, mutual accountability, and adaptive capacity, qualities essential to navigating the uncertainties and interdependencies of energy transitions. By anchoring innovation within a collaborative governance structure, European ports can accelerate their transformation into sustainable, resilient, and smart energy hubs. This approach ensures that technological advancements are not pursued in isolation but rather co-designed with the communities, institutions, and industries they are meant to serve. As Europe leads the global shift towards a climate-neutral economy, its ports—guided by inclusive and adaptive governance—will serve as critical accelerators of the green transition.

To operationalize such a model, this document proposes a Collaborative Governance Framework tailored to the realities of European ports and based on the example of the Port of Aalborg and the Port of Trelleborg. It focuses on four integrated pillars: stakeholder value creation, resource optimization, digital communication strategies, governance, and policy alignment. The proposed approach of the POTENT-X project to this framework relies on the creation of tailored Living Labs in the two pilot ports: Port of Aalborg (PoA) and Port of Trelleborg (PoT).

A Living Lab (LL) is a co-creation platform that enables collaborative innovation in real-world environments through iterative development and stakeholder engagement. These platforms bring together actors from the Quadruple Helix—public sector, private sector, academia, and civil society—to jointly design, test, and refine sustainable solutions, particularly in complex ecosystems such as ports.

Main Pillars of a Living Lab include:

1. Co-Creation – All stakeholders actively participate in the design and development of solutions.
2. Real-Life Testing – Solutions are tested in operational, real-world environments rather than isolated labs.

3. Multistakeholder Ecosystem – Engagement across government, industry, research, and community actors.
4. Iteration C Feedback Loops – Continuous refinement based on empirical data and stakeholder input.
5. Value Co-Creation – Focus on generating shared value, both technically and socially.

In the port context, Living Labs offer a powerful means of piloting clean energy technologies (e.g., shore power, green hydrogen, electrified cargo handling), aligning investment strategies, and building consensus around shared sustainability objectives given the hierarchical and functional structure of a LL (Fig.1).

Fig. 1 - Hierarchical and functional structure of a Living Lab in a port context piloting clean energy technologies such as electrified cargo handling and green hydrogen.

The framework draws on interdisciplinary knowledge and EU-funded initiatives, including Horizon Europe, CEF Transport, and ENOLL (European Network of Living Labs). It also aligns with emerging best practices from Smart Port projects in Antwerp, Rotterdam, Hamburg, and Valencia—ports that have become frontrunners in deploying digital twins, integrating renewable energy systems, and fostering cross-sector partnerships.

This document outlines a unified framework for collaborative governance, specifically tailored to facilitate the clean energy transition through Living Lab-based port networks, highlighting best practices and key examples, digital transformation, and industrial innovation enabling ports to become testbeds for scalable solutions, aligning economic growth with environmental sustainability for the clean energy transition in ports.

2 Stakeholder Engagement and Value Creation

Objective of this pillar: Build a multi-actor collaboration ecosystem to drive innovation and sustainability.

A key objective of this framework is to build a multi-actor collaboration ecosystem to drive innovation and sustainability. This is achieved, in a first phase, through the identification and engagement of key stakeholders across several sectors. The stakeholders include the public sector (port authorities, policymakers, environmental agencies), private sector actors (energy providers, logistics companies, technology firms, shipowners), academia and research institutions focusing on clean energy and digital transformation, and community organizations (local communities, environmental NGOs, citizen groups).

2.1 Multi-stakeholder Mapping: building the Living Lab of the port of Aalborg

Effective stakeholder mapping is foundational to building a collaborative governance model that supports the clean energy transition in European ports. Given the highly interconnected and multi-sectoral nature of port ecosystems, stakeholder mapping must go beyond identification to include analysis of influence, interests, power dynamics, and potential synergies. This ensures that all relevant actors are not only involved but strategically positioned in decision-making and co-creation processes.

Multi-stakeholder mapping enables ports to foster alignment across institutional, industrial, and community boundaries. It supports transparency, trust-building, and targeted engagement—critical components in overcoming resistance, identifying shared goals, and designing equitable energy solutions.

European ports, in particular, are increasingly at the forefront of climate policy implementation. Initiatives such as the European Green Deal, the "Fit for 55" package, and the EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Finance provide both pressure and opportunity for transformative change. As complex sociotechnical systems, ports require governance models that are inclusive, adaptive, and innovation-driven.

The following focuses on the methodology and results obtained in early workshop sessions at the port of Aalborg (DK) towards the development of an LL.

2.2 Methodology: Stakeholder Mapping Using the Quadruple Helix Model

The stakeholder mapping conducted during the first workshop at the port of Aalborg followed a structured, participatory methodology grounded in the Quadruple Helix Model. This model provided both a conceptual framework and a practical tool to identify, categorize, and engage stakeholders relevant to the development of the Port of Aalborg Living Lab.

2.2.1 Understanding the Quadruple Helix Model

The Quadruple Helix Model expands upon the traditional Triple Helix of innovation—which includes academia, industry, and government—by incorporating a fourth and equally critical dimension: civil society. This fourth strand recognizes the role of citizens, communities, NGOs, and end users in shaping innovation outcomes, especially in contexts involving public value creation and sustainability (Fig.2).

Fig. 2 - Quadruple helix model with each type of stakeholder group with distinct motivations, knowledge assets, and influence.

The model emphasizes the co-creation of knowledge and solutions, where innovation emerges through interactions among these diverse groups. In the Living Lab context, this means that solutions are not only technically feasible and commercially viable but also socially desirable and aligned with public interests.

2.2.2 Application in Stakeholder Mapping

During the workshop, participants applied the Quadruple Helix Model as a lens for stakeholder identification and engagement. The process began with an open brainstorming exercise in which participants listed all relevant actors connected to the Port of Aalborg context. As stakeholders were identified, they were categorized into one of the four helix domains. This categorization helped ensure balanced representation and highlighted potential gaps in engagement (e.g., missing civil society voices)(Fig.3).

Fig. 3 - Results of the brain dumping exercise at PoA in May 2025. Source: ENOLL (2025)

The model also guided discussions around value exchange. Participants reflected on what each helix contributes to the Living Lab and what incentives or outcomes would motivate their sustained involvement. For instance:

- Researchers might seek data access and real-world validation for theoretical models.
- Private companies could benefit from early testing of technologies or new market insights.
- Public authorities may be driven by sustainability objectives and policy alignment.
- Citizens and community groups might prioritize local environmental impact or improved quality of life.

By structuring the mapping process around the Quadruple Helix, the methodology ensured a systemic and inclusive approach to stakeholder engagement. It also laid the foundation for co-creation by revealing mutual dependencies, identifying shared interests, and fostering cross-sectoral dialogue from the outset of the Living Lab design.

Fig. 4 - Results of the exercise of the stakeholder value creation at PoA in May 2025. Source: ENoLL (2025)

This stakeholder mapping process, supported by visual tools (physical canvases and digital Miro boards), was not only descriptive but strategic, providing a roadmap for targeted engagement, value alignment, and long-term partnership building within the LL (Fig.4).

Finally, the third exercise, which was not completed during the workshop and scheduled for follow-up, involved formulating problem statements for each stakeholder group. The aim of this step is to define the key challenges, needs, or motivations of each stakeholder in their own context. By articulating these problem statements, the workshop seeks to deepen understanding of the interests driving each actor’s participation and help shape more targeted engagement strategies.

2.3 Best Practices in the Port of Aalborg

2.3.1 Co-Design Engagement Frameworks

The Port of Aalborg exemplifies how co-design principles can be operationalized at scale. Stakeholder engagement is deeply embedded in both its local and national sustainability initiatives. At the industrial level, PoA collaborates closely with strategic actors like Aalborg Portland on decarbonization pathways, including carbon capture initiatives, and with international partners such as Norne and Fidelis New Energy to advance CO₂ storage

infrastructure in Denmark. These multi-level engagements are formalized through long-term agreements and letters of intent, ensuring shared risk and mutual accountability from the outset (Fig.5).

Co-design frameworks are also used in shaping the port’s microgrid feasibility study. Stakeholders, including SMEs, energy providers, and regulatory bodies, are involved in shaping the objectives and evaluating implementation potential, underscoring the importance of early and iterative consultation in energy system transitions.

Fig. 5 - Map of the Port of Aalborg ´s larger Industrial Symbioses project called GRØN – Green Resource-Ecosystems North that successfully supports more than 80 companies to collaborate and develop new business models.

2.3.2 Use of Digital Tools

Digital stakeholder mapping platforms (e.g., Stakeholder Circle, Polinode) allow ports to visualize stakeholder ecosystems, simulate engagement impacts, and manage communication strategies effectively.

Digital tools at PoA are used not only for visualization and mapping but also to model synergies in industrial symbiosis. In the GRØN – Green Resource-Ecosystems North project, PoA facilitated the development of a digital map that identified resource-sharing opportunities between more than 80 companies. The visualizations enabled a systemic understanding of surplus flows—materials, energy, logistics—and led to new circular business models.

Additionally, PoA uses graphical illustrations of stakeholder mapping exercises to communicate internal logic and value exchange clearly among actors. These tools enhance transparency and engagement during workshops and Living Lab design sessions.

2.3.3 Inclusivity Mechanisms

At the local scale, PoA emphasizes inclusivity by actively involving both large industry clusters (e.g. wind energy sector leaders like Siemens Gamesa and CS Wind Offshore) and local SMEs in innovation ecosystems. The port’s approach to industrial symbiosis—facilitated through partnerships with Aalborg University—has enabled smaller actors to participate in collaborative projects that generate mutual benefit and reduce environmental impact (Fig.6). These inclusive models also extend to logistical sharing, co-location strategies, and knowledge exchange mechanisms.

Fig. 6 - Key results of the Industrial Symbioses per SME company.

2.3.4 Embedded Living Labs

The Port of Aalborg integrates Living Lab thinking across its development strategy. The microgrid feasibility study, for instance, is being scoped with a potential Living Lab format in mind, treating it as a testing ground for energy communities, grid balancing, and renewable integration. In this context, the Living Lab is seen not as a standalone project but as a dynamic,

adaptive governance format that enables co-creation of regulatory, technical, and economic solutions.

The industrial symbiosis network developed under the GRØN project further reflects embedded Living Lab characteristics: co-creation, facilitation by a trusted intermediary (PoA), and iterative development of circular business models through real-world experiments.

2.3.5 Policy Integration

Governance alignment at PoA reflects an integrated policy-awareness approach. Local projects are analyzed in light of gaps across global, European, and national regulatory levels. For example, the PoA microgrid project revealed that Danish regulations—such as the Electricity Supply Act (1999) and the Law on Ports (1999)—may hinder microgrid deployment. To overcome this, PoA proposes the establishment of a regulatory sandbox that enables controlled testing of new technologies and models under temporarily adjusted legal frameworks. The sandbox approach is positioned as a tool for adaptive governance, aligning with EU-level ambitions (e.g. AFIR, RED II/III, EU ETS) while fostering innovation within constrained national frameworks.

2.4 Green Shipping Corridor Partnership: Lübeck-Trelleborg

In 2025, the Port of Lübeck, the Port of Trelleborg, and TT-Line formalized their commitment to decarbonized shipping through a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) establishing a Green Shipping Corridor. A Green Shipping Corridor is a specific maritime route between two or more ports where stakeholders collaborate to deploy low- or zero-emission vessels and supporting infrastructure, with the aim of accelerating decarbonization and reducing the environmental impact of shipping along that route. This trilateral partnership is a practical application of collaborative governance, aligning with the Clydebank Declaration's goal to facilitate decarbonization through green corridors. By forming a Living Lab-style partnership involving port authorities, ferry operators, and national governments, the corridor aims to develop scalable decarbonization models covering maritime operations, hinterland logistics, and terminal systems. The agreement commits stakeholders to jointly address regulatory and technological barriers, while also seeking endorsement and support from both Swedish and German authorities.

2.5 Other Key European Examples

2.5.1 Port of Rotterdam – Digital Twin and Hydrogen Valley Initiatives

Rotterdam has adopted a dynamic stakeholder mapping system within its Digital Twin and H2PORTS projects. Stakeholders include Shell, Uniper, Delft University, and the Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure, all linked through a governance board that oversees shared KPIs and data transparency mechanisms.

2.5.2 Valencia Living Lab – H2020 CORE LNG as Hive Project

Valencia's Living Lab coordinated efforts between the Fundación Valenciaport, Enagás, the Spanish Maritime Safety Agency, and local ship operators. Stakeholder roles were explicitly defined and governed through a shared Memorandum of Understanding.

2.5.3 Port of Hamburg – Smart Port Logistics

In the SmartPORT Energy project, Hamburg uses a multi-tiered stakeholder governance model incorporating energy providers (Vattenfall), ICT firms (SAP), public bodies, and academia. Workshops, joint platforms, and scenario planning were used for mapping stakeholder expectations and responsibilities.

Multi-stakeholder mapping in European ports is not a one-time activity but a dynamic, iterative process embedded within the broader collaborative governance strategy. When executed effectively, it enables synergetic partnerships, reduces conflicts, and accelerates the design and deployment of clean energy solutions. By institutionalizing best practices—like co-design frameworks, digital mapping tools, and inclusive engagement protocols—European ports can transform from static infrastructures into adaptive innovation ecosystems that drive Europe's green and digital transitions.

With this foundation, Living Lab environments become not only spaces for technical experimentation but also arenas for institutional innovation—anchoring Europe's port sector at the forefront of sustainable development and energy innovation.

3 Resource Optimization and Technology Integration

Objective of this pillar: Enhance efficiency, minimize carbon footprint, and integrate smart energy solutions.

This section focuses on enhancing the efficiency of port operations, minimizing the carbon footprint, and integrating smart energy solutions. A Port Energy Transition Roadmap is critical to defining short-, medium-, and long-term clean energy adoption targets, such as shore power, hydrogen, and electrification. These targets should align with the EU Green Deal, Fit for 55, and IMO decarbonization goals.

3.1 Port Energy Transition Roadmap

Developing a clear and actionable Port Energy Transition Roadmap is critical to guiding long-term sustainable development. This roadmap should include specific targets tailored to the port's geography, traffic profile, and emissions baseline.

For example: ports may aim to achieve 100% electrification of berths by 2030, ensuring that vessels can connect to shore power and shut off auxiliary engines while docked. Similarly, by 2035, ports should be hydrogen-ready, with the necessary infrastructure in place to support hydrogen-fueled equipment and vessels. These targets help reduce fossil fuel dependency while also offering measurable indicators of environmental performance.

A central component of this roadmap involves establishing carbon budgets for each operational zone within the port. By assigning a maximum allowable emissions threshold to individual areas—such as logistics terminals, storage yards, or shipping lanes—port authorities can better monitor decarbonization progress and target interventions more effectively. These carbon budgets also enable data-driven investment planning, helping prioritize clean energy and efficiency upgrades where they matter most.

Furthermore, all roadmap milestones should be formally embedded into the port's master planning framework. By integrating sustainability targets into infrastructure development strategies, procurement policies, and operational guidelines, ports can ensure coherence between their environmental ambitions and day-to-day decision-making.

3.2 Smart Energy Management

Smart energy management lies at the core of next-generation port operations. Artificial Intelligence (AI) platforms can be employed for predictive maintenance, optimizing equipment

usage, and anticipating energy demand fluctuations. These tools allow ports to shift from reactive to proactive energy strategies, reducing waste and minimizing downtime. Internet of Things (IoT) devices can enable real-time monitoring of energy consumption across onshore and offshore assets. When connected to an integrated platform, these sensors can facilitate dynamic load balancing, improve resilience during peak demand, and ensure smooth coordination with renewable energy inputs. Integrating energy storage systems, such as advanced battery installations, with local solar, wind, and tidal generators will support 24/7 green energy availability, even during supply disruptions.

In addition to AI, Internet of Things (IoT) technologies enable real-time monitoring of energy consumption across port facilities and equipment. By connecting sensors to an integrated control system, ports can dynamically balance energy loads between onshore facilities and offshore assets, preventing bottlenecks during peak demand periods. This real-time feedback loop also supports better integration of renewable energy sources, enhancing overall system resilience.

To ensure continuous access to clean energy, ports should also invest in advanced energy storage systems, such as large-scale batteries. When combined with local renewable energy inputs—such as solar panels, wind turbines, or tidal generators—these storage units can deliver consistent green electricity around the clock, even when intermittent generation or supply disruptions occur.

PoA is currently undertaking a feasibility study investigating the possibility for establishing a micro grid solution for a number of SMEs and larger industrial companies located in PoA Business Park.

The study is a preliminary business case based on energy system simulations and is expected to address the following key questions:

- a) Can the theoretical benefits be realized in reality and at what cost?
- b) Is it feasible to establish the system, or is the initial investment too big as compared to the short- and long-term benefits?
- c) What opportunities and challenges (regulatory in particular) exist in relation to the realization of the energy community, the system and the business model?

The aim is further to assist the decarbonisation process of the Port as well as the companies by using energy from the grid when the CO₂ footprint is low and possible store energy and/or producing own (renewable energy) for storage and use. Furthermore, a micro grid with balancing capacity could provide additional capacity to offset energy fall outs and spikes (build in resilience)(Fig.7).

PoA would like to explore the possibilities in applying a living lab approach to the on-going microgrid project as feasibility study is believed to be only the start of a possible realisation of the introduction of Microgrid as a tool for decarbonisation and building energy resilience.

Energy Community - Micro Grid

Energy Community – Micro Grid

- SWOT and preparatory work (2024)
- Feasibility study investigating opportunities for establishing a local micro grid solution for at select number of companies in the business Park of PoA (on-going 2025)
- Outcome – possibly answer to the following key questions:
 - Can the theoretical benefits be realized in reality and at what investment?
 - Is it worth establishing the system, or is the initial investment too large compared to the short- and long-term benefits?
 - What opportunities and challenges exist in relation to the realization of the energy community, the system and the business model?
- Way forward and decision to further investigate, invest or postpone/abolish investment decision (2026)

Fig. 7 - Outlines of the SWOT analysis of the Micro Grid project in the Port of Aalborg.

3.3 Joint Roadmap for Zero-Emission Corridor: Lübeck-Trelleborg

The ports of Lübeck and Trelleborg have committed to reaching net-zero emissions by 2040, a goal shared by TT-Line in its fleet modernization plans. As part of the Green Shipping Corridor MoU, the partners aim to create a phased roadmap incorporating low- and zero-emission technologies across port terminals, hinterland logistics, and shipping activities. This includes establishing shore-side electricity supply, incentivizing green fuel usage, optimizing port operations, and upgrading hinterland intermodal transport. The joint roadmap functions as a real-world testbed for replicable low-emission transport chains, offering clear performance targets and an integrated transition path for the entire corridor.

3.4 Circular Economy Initiatives

Incorporating circular economy principles is another key dimension of resource optimization. Integrating circular economy principles into port operations is essential for enhancing environmental sustainability and resource efficiency, as circular economy initiatives naturally complement the port energy transition by reducing waste, extending the lifecycle of materials, and optimizing resource use, thereby decreasing the overall energy demand of port operations. Practices such as waste heat recovery, reuse of construction materials, and valorization of industrial by-products support decarbonization while creating local value chains. In the Living Lab context, circular logistics and material flow monitoring help identify synergies between resource efficiency and clean energy systems, such as integrating waste-to-energy technologies or electrifying reuse logistics. This systemic thinking strengthens resilience and reinforces the sustainability of the energy transition at the port scale. Circular economy principles can further enhance environmental and economic performance in ports. By transforming waste materials into valuable resources, ports can reduce their environmental footprint and contribute to broader ecological restoration and economic development goals.

The port of Seville management showcases several best practices in circular economy (espo.be/news/port-of-sevilla-wins-the-espo-award-2024):

Example 1: Reusing Dredged Sediments for Coastal Restoration and Biodiversity Enhancement

The Port of Seville has pioneered the sustainable reuse of dredged sediments through its Navigation Optimization Project. This initiative aligns with the "Working with Nature" philosophy, aiming to improve navigability while promoting environmental stewardship. Uncontaminated fine sediments extracted during maintenance dredging are repurposed for

coastal restoration projects, such as regenerating the Doñana Natural Area and the beaches of Sanlúcar de Barrameda. These efforts not only restore eroded coastlines but also enhance habitats for aquatic birds and other wildlife, contributing to increased biodiversity in the region.

Example 2: Transforming Sediments into Sustainable Construction Materials

In collaboration with the company Todobarro, the Port of Seville is exploring innovative ways to convert dredged sediments into eco-friendly construction materials. This partnership focuses on producing compressed earth blocks and ceramic products using the extracted sediments. These materials are intended for use in bioclimatic architecture, offering sustainable alternatives to traditional construction methods. The initiative exemplifies how ports can contribute to the circular economy by creating new value chains from materials that would otherwise be considered waste.

Example 3: Enhancing Agricultural Soils with Sediment-Based Amendments

Beyond construction applications, the Port of Seville is investigating the use of dredged sediments to improve agricultural soils. By enriching soils with nutrient-rich sediments, the port aims to support local agriculture, enhance soil fertility, and promote sustainable farming practices. This approach demonstrates the multifaceted benefits of sediment reuse, extending the positive impacts of port operations to the agricultural sector.

Example 4: Creating New Wetlands for Ecosystem Services

The Port of Seville has also utilized dredged materials to create new wetlands within the estuary environment. These wetlands serve as critical habitats for various bird species and contribute to the overall ecological health of the region. By transforming disposal sites into functional ecosystems, the port showcases a commitment to environmental restoration and the provision of ecosystem services.

Additional Circular Economy Initiatives in ports:

- Port of Rotterdam, Netherlands: The port has established a "Waste-to-Chemicals" plant that converts non-recyclable waste into chemicals and biofuels, reducing landfill use and supporting the circular economy. (https://hollandcircularhotspot.nl/case/port-of-rotterdam-cooperation-on-a-local-level/?utm_source=chatgpt.com)
- Port of Antwerp, Belgium: Through the "Circular Port" initiative, Antwerp promotes the reuse of materials and energy within the port area, including the development of eco-effective industrial processes and the facilitation of industrial symbiosis among

companies (https://circularports.vlaanderen-circulair.be/cases/nextgent-district-antwerp/?utm_source=chatgpt.com)

- Port of Gothenburg, Sweden: Gothenburg has implemented a project to recover and reuse dredged materials for construction and landscaping purposes, minimizing waste and promoting sustainable resource use. (https://circularports.vlaanderen-circulair.be/cases/dredging-spoil-projects-in-the-port-of-gothenburg/?utm_source=chatgpt.com)

These examples illustrate how ports across Europe are adopting circular economy principles to enhance sustainability, reduce environmental impact, and foster innovation in port operations.

By adopting these circular economy initiatives, ports like Seville demonstrate how sustainable practices can be integrated into maritime operations, turning environmental challenges into opportunities for innovation and community engagement.

Lastly, innovative technologies such as carbon capture and CO₂-to-fuel conversion offer groundbreaking possibilities for ports with large industrial footprints. By piloting these systems in collaboration with energy companies and research institutions, ports can transform captured carbon emissions into synthetic fuels that are suitable for maritime or land-based transport. If successful, such pilots could be scaled up and replicated across multiple industrial port zones, making a significant contribution to long-term energy diversification and climate neutrality.

4 Digital Communication Strategies for Energy Transition

Objective of this pillar: Leverage digital communication tools and platforms to enhance transparency, build trust, and facilitate real-time, cross-sector collaboration across the port innovation ecosystem.

4.1 Developing Digital Twin Models of Port Infrastructure

Effective communication and the seamless sharing of data are fundamental to advancing transparency, building trust among stakeholders, and enabling cross-sector collaboration in the context of sustainable port development. The deployment of digital tools such as open data platforms and digital twin technologies plays a pivotal role in this process. Digital twins—virtual replicas of physical systems—are transforming port operations by enabling simulation, monitoring, and optimization of clean energy and logistics scenarios. These tools allow for real-time monitoring of key indicators such as energy consumption and carbon emissions, while also enabling the simulation and optimization of energy flows across complex port systems. By offering predictive insights, digital twins can inform policy-making and operational decisions under various scenarios, enhancing the adaptability and resilience of port infrastructure (European Commission, 2023). Digital twins act as strategic enablers for port decarbonization and logistics efficiency. By simulating and optimizing clean energy scenarios, equipment use, and shipping flows—before committing to real-world implementation—ports enhance sustainability, resilience, and competitiveness. This aligns digital innovation with environmental goals in today’s smarter maritime ecosystems.

Table 1 - Benefits for Clean Energy C Operation from Digital Twins.

Features	Benefit
Clean Energy Scenario Modelling	Simulate impacts of electrification (e.g., shore power, hybrid cranes) before deployment.
Equipment Use Optimization	Use predictive maintenance to reduce downtime, saving energy and operational costs.
Shipping Flow Simulation	Model vessel arrival/departure to optimize routing and limit emissions.
Emergency Preparedness	Test responses to extreme weather, power outages, or pollution incidents.
Performance Monitoring	Compare “simulated” vs. “real-time” efficiency to assess clean technology adoption.

4.2 Key Examples

4.2.1 Port of Trelleborg (Sweden) – Corridor Monitoring between Lübeck and Trelleborg

While the MoU does not yet detail a digital twin application, the corridor concept lends itself to real-time digital coordination of emissions, fuel use, and vessel arrivals. Future integration of monitoring systems and cross-border data exchange is planned as the corridor develops. Early digital integration will support emissions benchmarking and transparency across corridor operations.

4.2.2 Port of Rotterdam (Netherlands)

The Port of Rotterdam collaborates with IBM, Esri, Cisco, Axians, and others to build a real-time digital twin capturing real-world data via IoT sensors on cranes, quay walls, buoys, and more. This virtual model:

- Simulates energy flows and vessel movements.
- Optimizes ship berthing to reduce idle time—helping save fuel and limit emissions.
- Predicts ideal docking times, potentially saving up to USD 80 000 per ship [hapag-lloyd.com+10ditto-oceandecade.org+10sinay.ai+10ditto-oceandecade.org+2ibm.com+2piernext.portdebarcelona.cat+2](#).

A related Deltares project, DigiPACT, uses digital twin data to guide ship speed and routing to minimize CO₂ and particulate emissions—demonstrating real-time "green steaming" capabilities [deltalife.deltares.nl+1convergence.nl+1](#).

4.2.3 Singapore Maritime Digital Twin (Tuas Port)

Singapore's Maritime Digital Twin (MDT), developed by MPA and GovTech, integrates sensor, vessel, and environmental data to simulate complex port dynamics. Key benefits:

- Reduced wait times and vessel congestion, leading to **faster turnaround** and lower emissions.
- Predictive crisis modeling—such as typhoons or equipment failure—for planning resilience.

- Enables testing of **emerging energy-efficient technologies** (e.g., shore power integration) without operational risk worldports.org.

4.2.4 Port of Livorno (Italy)

Since 2016, Livorno has deployed a digital twin using 5G, AI, WDR cameras, and VR interfaces to:

- Track cargo and equipment movements in real time.
- Simulate loading/unloading operations to reduce dwell times and carbon emissions.
- Empower operators to visualize and optimize logistics flows convergence.nl+3sinay.ai+3hapag-lloyd.com+3convergence.nl+2mdpi.com+2compacer.com+2compacer.com.

4.2.5 Port of Antwerp–Bruges (Belgium)

The APICA digital twin integrates geographic data (waterways, roads, rail, environment), enabling:

- Precise monitoring of energy usage (e.g., shore power, smart grid systems).
- Event triggering (e.g., drone inspections) based on real-time sensor alerts.
- Energy optimization through predictive modeling and environmental simulations piernext.portdebarcelona.cat+1portofrotterdam.com+1.

5 Governance and Policy Alignment

Objective of this pillar: Ensure regulatory compliance and long-term sustainability in port operations.

5.1 Policy Framework and Compliance

Ensuring regulatory compliance and long-term sustainability in port operations is essential for the successful implementation of clean energy strategies. This requires alignment with the EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Finance, the Renewable Energy Directive, and the Emission Trading System (ETS). Port-specific decarbonization action plans should be developed to guide these efforts.

Establishing robust governance structures and aligning policy frameworks are critical for ensuring the long-term sustainability and regulatory compliance of clean energy transitions in port operations. This involves adhering to major EU-level directives and regulatory instruments, including the EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Finance, the Renewable Energy Directive (RED II and RED III), and the evolving EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS)(Fig.8). These frameworks collectively shape investment eligibility, emissions reduction targets, and the integration of renewable energy sources into critical infrastructure (European Commission, 2022a; European Parliament, 2023).

Fig. 8 - Steps for achieving policy alignment.

Port authorities should be proactive in mapping existing local regulations and operational protocols against these overarching EU frameworks to identify gaps and opportunities.

Embedding compliance metrics into port concession agreements, leasing contracts, and performance monitoring systems will help institutionalize sustainability as a core operational principle. This ensures that both public and private stakeholders remain accountable for achieving decarbonization targets over the long term (European Court of Auditors, 2021).

Example of the Port of Trelleborg

The Green Shipping Corridor initiative between Lübeck and Trelleborg is explicitly anchored in international and national governance frameworks, including Germany and Sweden's commitment to the Clydebank Declaration. The MoU commits the partners to engage with national governments to secure alignment with policy frameworks, incentives, and compliance tools. It also includes exploration of risk-sharing and funding mechanisms—potentially positioning this corridor as a testbed for regulatory sandboxes across EU jurisdictions. As such, the corridor initiative serves not only as a decarbonization pilot but also as a governance innovation platform, reflecting a multilayered policy integration approach.

5.2 Adaptive Regulatory Sandboxes

Adaptive regulatory sandboxes offer a structured, time-limited environment where emerging clean technologies can be tested under a flexible regulatory framework. They serve as innovation accelerators for port authorities and industry partners, enabling experimentation while mitigating legal, operational, and financial risks.

Definition and Strategic Role

A regulatory sandbox is a controlled setting in which selected innovations can be deployed under temporary exemptions or modified compliance conditions. In the context of ports, these sandboxes are instrumental for testing:

- Hydrogen and ammonia bunkering infrastructure
- Shore-side power integration (cold ironing)
- Electrified or autonomous cargo handling equipment
- Battery swapping for electric trucks or vessels
- Smart grid and energy storage pilots
- Circular economy and waste-to-energy solutions

They serve a dual function:

- Innovation Enablement – Allowing early-stage technologies to be deployed with institutional support and monitored closely.
- Evidence-Based Policy Development – Providing regulators with empirical data to inform future updates of legal and operational frameworks.

Implementation Steps:

1. Select eligible innovation domains: Prioritize clean energy technologies with high uncertainty or regulatory ambiguity.
2. Define evaluation criteria: Include safety, environmental performance, and economic feasibility.
3. Enable multi-stakeholder governance: Involve regulators, industry, insurance providers, and research institutions.
4. Introduce risk-sharing tools: Deploy public-private insurance and guarantees to protect early adopters from unforeseen liabilities.

Fig. G - Cascading governance gaps in Denmark.

In the context of the PoA Microgrid project, a feasibility study is likely to reveal that the current Danish regulatory framework—particularly the Electricity Supply Act and the Law on Ports, both enacted in 1999—presents significant barriers to the development and deployment of microgrids in Danish ports (Fig.9). These outdated regulations may hinder innovation and the implementation of circular energy models.

As a result, establishing a regulatory sandbox could be a strategic next step. This approach would enable stakeholders to test microgrid solutions in a real-world, low-risk environment—such as a LL—without immediately overhauling the existing legal framework.

Steps to Establish a Regulatory Sandbox in the case of the microgrid project of PoA:

Creating a sandbox to support circular economy projects, like microgrids, requires a flexible and collaborative structure. The following 10 steps offer a roadmap for building and operating such a framework:

1. Define the Purpose and Scope – Clarify what the sandbox aims to test and achieve.
2. Design the Regulatory and Governance Framework – Determine oversight structures and compliance boundaries.
3. Develop Criteria for Participation – Set transparent eligibility requirements for entities joining the sandbox.
4. Define Monitoring and Evaluation Metrics – Identify how success and impact will be measured.
5. Foster Collaboration Among Stakeholders – Include regulators, businesses, academia, and communities.
6. Provide Incentives and Support Mechanisms – Encourage innovation through grants, access to data, or technical support.
7. Test, Monitor, and Refine – Iterate based on real-world feedback and lessons learned.
8. Scale and Integrate – Transition successful models into mainstream policy and regulation.
9. Communicate Results and Build Public Trust – Maintain transparency to earn credibility and engagement.
10. Evaluate and Iterate – Continuously improve the sandbox model based on outcomes and stakeholder input.

5.3 Social and Economic Impact Assessments

Sustainable governance must also address social equity and economic resilience. The following steps help ensure an inclusive transition:

Step 1: Model Job and Economic Impacts

Use scenario-based modeling to assess how energy transition strategies will affect employment in logistics, maritime operations, and maintenance.

Step 2: Develop Training and Reskilling Pathways

Co-create targeted curricula with:

- Local universities
- Vocational schools
- Trade unions

These programs should anticipate skill shifts required for electric, hydrogen, and digital infrastructure.

Step 3: Conduct Environmental Justice Audits

Use equity-focused audits to evaluate how benefits (e.g. cleaner air, new jobs, subsidies) and burdens (e.g. job displacement, construction noise) are distributed. Adjust project plans to mitigate negative impacts and promote fairness.

Example: In the Port of Los Angeles, a similar audit led to re-routing a clean truck program to serve neighborhoods with the highest air pollution burden.

6 Conclusions

Ports are central to Europe's trade and economic strength but remain high-emission zones in need of urgent transformation. The POTENT X project proposes a Collaborative Governance Framework to guide ports through a clean energy transition that is inclusive, efficient, and adaptive. Focusing on stakeholder engagement, resource optimization, digital communication, and policy alignment, this approach provides a comprehensive model grounded in real-world Living Lab experiences, particularly those of the Ports of Aalborg and Trelleborg. This brief distills the key lessons and policy insights from these efforts, offering guidance for port authorities, national regulators, and European institutions to coordinate and accelerate this vital transformation.

6.1 Strategic Overview

Stakeholder engagement lies at the heart of the governance model. By applying the Quadruple Helix approach, which brings together public institutions, private industry, academic researchers, and civil society, the framework ensures that energy solutions are not only technically feasible but socially desirable. The Port of Aalborg demonstrates how over 80 organizations can collaborate through shared digital tools and co-creation sessions to identify synergies, reduce carbon emissions, and promote industrial symbiosis. Workshops held there revealed how inclusive mapping and value exchange exercises help build long-term cooperation, allowing the port to act as both a coordinator and catalyst for sustainability. This stakeholder architecture becomes even more potent when embedded within a Living Lab format, enabling continuous testing, learning, and innovation in real operational settings. The partnership between the Ports of Lübeck and Trelleborg, formalized through a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with TT-Line, is another compelling example. It represents a trilateral commitment to establishing a Green Shipping Corridor under the Clydebank Declaration, with full alignment from national governments. This corridor functions as a Living Lab for port and maritime decarbonization, incorporating shore power, alternative fuels, and hinterland intermodal optimization.

Resource optimization is addressed through a dual strategy: the implementation of Port Energy Transition Roadmaps and the integration of circular economy principles. These roadmaps offer ports a structured way to set and track clean energy goals such as 100 percent shore power capability or hydrogen infrastructure readiness. At Aalborg, feasibility studies for a local microgrid are being used to assess the viability of decentralized energy solutions. The project considers not only technological options but also regulatory and business-model challenges, recognizing that many of the obstacles to innovation are institutional rather than technical. Meanwhile, ports such as Seville and Rotterdam have demonstrated how circular economy initiatives—from sediment reuse to waste-to-chemicals conversion—can reduce environmental impact and simultaneously create new value chains. In parallel, Lübeck and Trelleborg have committed to net-zero operations by 2040 and are collaborating to implement a phased decarbonization strategy encompassing port operations, shipping, and logistics. This shared roadmap includes not only infrastructure upgrades but also business model innovations and risk-sharing mechanisms to incentivize private investment.

Digital communication strategies are a further pillar of the framework. In ports, data transparency, simulation, and real-time responsiveness are all essential to coordinating energy systems and stakeholder expectations. Digital twin technologies provide virtual replicas of infrastructure, allowing for scenario testing of energy usage, predictive maintenance, and emissions management before real-world deployment. The Port of Rotterdam and Singapore's Tuas Port illustrate how such tools can significantly reduce energy waste and improve operational decisions. Through integration with open data platforms and predictive models, ports can simulate vessel movements, optimize energy flow, and assess infrastructure resilience—an especially critical feature in an era of climate volatility. In the Lübeck–Trelleborg corridor, the integration of monitoring systems and data exchange mechanisms is anticipated to play a key role in tracking emissions and optimizing corridor logistics over time.

Policy alignment and governance reforms are essential to ensure that technical innovations translate into systemic change. The framework recommends full integration of EU directives such as the Renewable Energy Directive, the Emissions Trading System, and the EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Finance into local port strategies. Governance measures should include embedding sustainability indicators into leasing contracts, updating port regulations to allow new energy models, and establishing multi-actor innovation committees. Adaptive regulatory sandboxes are identified as a key enabler, allowing for experimental deployment of emerging technologies—like hydrogen fueling stations or autonomous electrified cargo systems—under flexible legal conditions. The Port of Aalborg's microgrid initiative highlights the need to modernize outdated laws, such as Denmark's 1999 Electricity Supply Act, that currently hinder decarbonization efforts. Similarly, the Lübeck–Trelleborg MoU envisions engagement with national regulators in Germany and Sweden to facilitate green corridor implementation, including policy incentives and cross-border compliance mechanisms.

In parallel, social and economic dimensions must be addressed to ensure a just transition. This includes modeling job impacts, developing new curricula for port workers, and conducting environmental justice audits to assess whether clean energy benefits are equitably distributed. By aligning workforce development with infrastructure modernization, ports can secure both social acceptance and economic resilience during the transition.

6.2 Policy Implications and Recommendations

To operationalize this framework at scale, policymakers should formally recognize Living Labs as innovation instruments within port governance. These Labs should be given a structural role in port master planning, with defined mandates and access to national and EU-level funding. Regulatory frameworks must evolve to allow for adaptive experimentation through legal sandboxes, particularly in areas with rapidly changing technologies like green fuels and digital systems. Clean energy roadmaps should be made mandatory for ports receiving EU infrastructure funds, with performance benchmarks tied to key milestones in emissions reduction, renewable integration, and energy efficiency.

It is equally important to embed circular economy mandates into port concession agreements and procurement policies, allowing for the reuse of materials and the reduction of lifecycle emissions. The creation of a shared European digital platform would enable cross-port knowledge exchange, real-time monitoring, and open collaboration between stakeholders. Such a platform could facilitate emissions tracking, pilot reporting, and stakeholder mapping across Living Labs.

Finally, every clean energy port initiative should include a social component. Policy measures must ensure that job creation, training, and community benefits are not left behind in the race to decarbonize. Equity audits, workforce transition strategies, and public participation channels will be key to achieving both environmental and societal legitimacy.

The energy transition in ports is not just a technical or financial issue; it is a governance challenge that demands inclusive, agile, and evidence-based approaches. The POTENT X Collaborative Governance Framework demonstrates how European ports can become testbeds for innovation while remaining accountable to climate, economic, and social objectives. By embedding collaborative governance, smart technology, and adaptive regulation into the fabric of port operations, Europe can position its ports as global leaders in the green transition.

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